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Research Article

Integrated In Silico and In Vitro Investigation of Antimicrobial Activity of *Morinda citrifolia* Ethanolic Extract

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ABSTRACT

Morinda citrifolia (Noni) is a medicinal plant widely used in traditional medicine for its antimicrobial properties. The present study aimed to evaluate the antimicrobial activity of *Morinda citrifolia* (Flowers) extract using nutrient broth medium, disc diffusion method, agar well diffusion method, and serial dilution techniques. Phytochemical screening was performed to identify active compounds, and molecular docking studies were carried out to analyze the interaction between phytoconstituents and microbial target proteins. The extract showed significant inhibition against selected microorganisms compared to blank control. Percentage inhibition was calculated using serial dilution results. Molecular docking revealed strong binding affinity of bioactive compounds with bacterial protein targets, supporting the experimental findings. The study confirms the antimicrobial potential of *Morinda citrifolia* and explains its mechanism at the molecular level.

INTRODUCTION

An antimicrobial is an agent that kills microorganisms (microbicide) or stops their growth (bacteriostatic agent). Antimicrobial medicines can be grouped according to the microorganisms they are used to treat.

For example, antibiotics are used against bacteria, and antifungals are used against fungi. They can also be classified according to their function.

Antimicrobial medicines to treat infection are known as antimicrobial chemotherapy, while antimicrobial drugs are used to prevent infection, which known as antimicrobial prophylaxis.

The main classes of antimicrobial agents are disinfectants (non-selective agents, such as bleach), which kill a wide range of microbes on surfaces to prevent the spread of illness, antiseptics which are applied to living tissue and help reduce

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infection during surgery, and antibiotics which destroy microorganisms within the body.

ANTIFUNGALS

Antifungals are used to kill or prevent further growth of fungi. In medicine, they are used as a treatment for infections such as athlete's foot, ringworm and thrush and work by exploiting differences between mammalian and fungal cells. Unlike bacteria, both fungi and humans are eukaryotes.

ANTIVIRAL

Antiviral drugs are a class of medication used specifically for treating viral infections. Like antibiotics, specific antivirals are used for specific viruses. They should be distinguished from vermicides, which actively deactivate virus particles outside the body.

ANTIPARASITIC:

Antiparasitic are a class of medications which are indicated for the treatment of parasitic diseases, such as those caused by helminthes, amoeba, ectoparasites, parasitic fungi, and protozoa, among others. Antiparasitic target the parasitic agents of the infections by destroying them or inhibiting their growth; they are usually effective against a limited number of parasites within a Particular class

ANTIMICROBIAL

MECHANISM OF ACTION OF ANTI MICROBIALS:

1. Inhibition of Cell Wall Synthesis

- **Target:** Peptidoglycan layer in bacterial cell walls
- **Effect:** Weakens the cell wall, leading to cell lysis and death
- **Mainly active against:** Gram-positive bacteria

Examples: **β -lactams:** Penicillins, Cephalosporins, **Glycopeptides:** Vancomycin

2. Disruption of Cell Membrane Function

- **Target:** Cell membrane (phospholipid or sterol components)
- **Effect:** Destroys membrane integrity → leakage of vital molecules → cell death

Examples: **Polymyxins** (bacteria), **Amphotericin B**, **Nystatin** (fungi - target ergosterol)

3. Inhibition of Protein Synthesis

- **Target:** Bacterial ribosomes (30S or 50S subunits)
- **Effect:** Blocks protein production → inhibits growth or kills cell

Examples: **Tetracyclines**, **Aminoglycosides** (30S), **Macrolides**, **Chloramphenicol** (50S)

4. Inhibition of Nucleic Acid Synthesis

- **Target:** Enzymes for DNA or RNA replication
- **Effect:** Prevents DNA replication or transcription → halts cell division

Examples: **Fluoroquinolones** (inhibit DNA gyrase), **Rifampin** (inhibits RNA polymerase)

5. Inhibition of Essential Metabolic Pathways

- **Target:** Enzymes in folic acid synthesis (used for DNA/RNA synthesis)

- **Effect:** Starves the cell of critical nutrients

Examples: Sulfonamide, Trimethoprim

PLANT PROFILE

NONI

- Family : Rubiaceae
- Subfamily : Rubioideae
- Genus : Morinda
- Species : Morinda citrifolia

Vernacular names:

English : Indian Mulberry

Tamil : Nuna

Hindi : Bartundi

Telugu : Mogali

Kannada : Tagase maddi

Common name: Indian Mulberry, Great Morinda, Cheese fruit,

Scientific name: *Morindia citrifolia*

Family : Rubiaceae

Geographical source: Kerala, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu

Scientific classification:

- Kingdom : Plantae
- Order : Gentianales

Description:

Morinda citrifolia is a shrub or small tree up to 6 m tall, with grey-brown bark. The twigs are more or less square in cross-section and often fleshy. Stipules are present, very broad and obtuse at the apex, measuring up to 2 cm wide and long. The large glabrous leaves are elliptic to ovate in shape and have 6–9 pairs of lateral veins. The flowers are white and tubular with five lobes, measuring about 15 cm long and across.

The fruits are initially green, transitioning through pale yellow to white or grey, and when ripe they emit a pungent odour. They are irregularly ellipsoid or ovoid.

Chemical constituent:

Morinda citrifolia fruit powder contains carbohydrates and dietary fibre in moderate amounts. These macronutrients reside in the fruit pulp, as *M. citrifolia* juice has sparse nutrient content. *Morinda citrifolia* fruit contains diverse phytochemicals, including anthraquinones, lignans, oligo- and polysaccharides, flavonoids, iridoids, such as deacetylasperulosidic acid, scopoletin, fatty acids, catechin, beta-sitosterol, damnacanthal, and alkaloids.

Pharmacological profile:

- Antibacterial
- Antiviral
- Antifungal
- Anthelmintic
- Antitumor
- Analgesic
- Hypotensive
- Anti-inflammatory
- Immune - enhancing effect.

MOLECULAR DESIGN:

Molecular design is the process of finding new medicines based on the knowledge of a biological target, it enabled the chemist to predict the structure and then it also allows the medicinal chemist to evaluate the interaction between a

compound and its target site before synthesizing a compound so as to increase the ability by reducing the side effects.

Various software used :

- Chem Sketch
- Mol inspiration
- Swiss ADME
- Pro Tox 3.0

MOL INSPIRATION

This software is used to calculate the following properties

- Log P
- Molecular weight
- Number of H-bond donor
- Number of H-bond acceptor
- Number of rotatable bonds

In addition to “LIPINSKI’S RULE” another rule was proposed VEBER he states that the number of rotatable bonds should be less than 10. This rule is more appropriate for oral drug only. According to the veber’s rule .

1. The Log P value should not be more than 5
2. The molecular weight of the compound should not more than 500
3. No. of H-bond donor not more than 5
4. No. of rotatable bonds should not be more than 10

3D STRUCTURAL VIEW OF COMPOUNDS:

URSANE

TANNIC ACID

CATECHIN

EPICATECHIN

DEACETYL ASPERULOSIDIC ACID(DAA)

ASPERULOSIDIC ACID(AA)

TIGOGENIN

OLEONANE

Table-1: Properties of Phytoconstituents

Sr. No	Phytoconstituents	PubChem Id	Molecular Weight	Molecular Formula
1	Scopoletin	5280460	192.17 g/mol	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄
2	Quercetine	5280343	302.23 g/mol	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇
3	Kaempferol	5280863	286.24 g/mol	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆
4	Rutin	6728944	610.5 g/mol	C ₂₇ H ₃₀ O ₁₆
5	Gallic Acid	370	170.12g/mol	C ₇ H ₆ O ₅
6	Caffeic Acid	689043	180.16g/mol	C ₉ H ₈ O ₄
7	Ursolic Acid	64945	456.7g/mol	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ O ₃
8	Oleanolic Acid	10494	456.7g/mol	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ O ₃
9	B-SITOSTEROL	222284	414.7g/mol	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O
10	Linalool	6549	154.25g/mol	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O
11	Tannic Acid	16129778	1701.2g/mol	C ₇₆ H ₅₂ O ₄₆
12	Catechin	9064	290.27g/mol	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₆
13	Epicatechin	72276	290.27g/mol	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₆
14	Deacetylasperulosidic Acid (DAA)	12315350	390.34g/mol	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₁
15	Asperulosidic Acid (AA)	119688	432.4g/mol	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₁₂
16	Tigogenin	99516	416.6 g/mol	C ₂₇ H ₄₄ O ₃
17	Oleanane	9548717	412.27 g/mol	C ₅₆ H ₉₂ O ₂₉
18	Ursane	9548870	412.7 g/mol	C ₃₀ H ₅₂

Table-2: ADME Properties of Phytoconstituents

Sr. No.	Phytoconstituents	Number of Rotatable Bonds	Number of Bond Acceptor	Number of Bond Donor	Lppgc/W9 (Liogl)	Molar Refractive	Solubility	Gastro Intestinal Absorption
1	Scopoletin	1	4	1	1.86	51.00	Soluble	High
2	Quercetine	1	7	5	1.63	78.03	Soluble	High
3	Kaempferol	1	6	4	1.70	76.01	Soluble	High
4	Rutin	6	16	10	0.46	141.38	Soluble	Low
5	Gallic Acid	1	5	4	0.21	39.47	Soluble	High
6	Caffeic Acid	2	4	3	0.97	47.16	Soluble	High
7	Ursolic Acid	1	3	2	3.95	136.91	Moderately Soluble	Low
8	Oleanolic Acid	1	3	2	3.94	136.65	Paartially Soluble	Low
9	B-Sitosterol	6	1	1	5.05	133.23	Partially Soluble	Low

10	Linalool	4	1	1	2.70	50.44	Soluble	High
11	Tannic Acid	10	19	11	0.36	142.56	Soluble	Low
12	Catechin	1	6	5	1.33	74.33	Soluble	High
13	Epicatechin	1	6	5	1.47	74.33	Soluble	High
14	Deacetyl Asperulosidic Acid (DAA)	5	11	7	0.58	83.73	Soluble	Low
15	Asperulosidic Acid (AA)	7	12	6	1.13	93.47	Soluble	Low
16	Tigogenin	7	13	1	4.53	122.07	Moderately .Soluble	High
17	Oleanane	0	0	0	5.05	134.19	Partially .Soluble	Low
18	Ursane	0	0	0	5.02	134.45	Partially .Soluble	Low

Table 3: Toxicity Study of Phytoconstituents

Sr. No	Phyto-Constituents	Nephlo Toxicity	Carcin o-toxicity	Cardio Toxicity	Muta Geneciy	Cyto Toxicity	Bbb-Barrier	Nutritiona l Toxicity	Aryl-Hydro-Carbon Receptor	Andro Gen Receptr
1	Scopoletin	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
2	Quercetin	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
3	Kaempferol	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
4	Rutin	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
5	Gallic Acid	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
6	Caffeic Acid	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
7	Ursolic Acid	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
8	Oleanolic Acid	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
9	B-Sitosterol	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
10	Linalool	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
11	Tannic Acid	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
12	Catechin	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
13	Epicatechin	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
14	Deacetyl- asperulosidic Acid (DAA)	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
15	Asperulo-Sidic Acid	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
16	Tigogenin	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
17	Oleanane	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
18	Ursane	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive

ANTI MICROBIAL ACTIVITY**CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF 1ULK****PREPARATION OF PROTEIN:**

The protein target, obtained from the RCSB protein data bank with the PDB accession. Code 1ULK function as docking receptor. The active site of the receptor was cleared of all sound ligands and water molecules.

PDB DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2210/pdb1ULK/pdb>

Classification: SUGAR BINDING PROTEIN

Organism(s): *Phytolacca americana*

Mutation(s): No

Experimental Data Snapshot

- Method: X-RAY DIFFRACTION
- Resolution: 1.80 Å
- R-Value Free: 0.203 (Depositor)
- R-Value Work: 0.176 (Depositor)
- R-Value Observed: 0.176 (Depositor)

BINDING AFFINITY

Sr. No	Phytoconstituents	Binding Affinity
1	Ciproflaxacin	-7.0023
2	Tannic Acid	-10.3872
3	Rutin	-8.1195
4	Beta Sitosterol	-7.4976
5	Asperulosidic Acid	-7.4150
6	Deacetyl Asperulosidic Acid (Daa)	-7.3563
7	Urasane	-7.0970
8	Ursolic Acid	-7.0485
9	Oleonane	-7.0445
10	Oleanolic Acid	-6.9786
11	Tigogenin	-6.7315
12	Epicatechin	-6.7252
13	Quercetin	-6.7019
14	Kaemferol	-6.6495
15	Catechin	-6.6175
16	Scopoletin	-6.2459
17	Linalool	-6.2316
18	Caffeic Acid	-6.1923
19	Gallic Acid	-5.8714

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Processing of plant :

The collected plant has identified by Dr.V.Suresh kumar, Assistant Professor, Dept of Botany, Government Arts College, Tiruvannamalai

(District), Tamilnadu, India. The plant was washed with tap water 3 times and sterilized by spraying with 70% alcohol.

The purified plant material was shade dried at room temperature to avoid chemical changes and frequently observed for any fungal contamination as the plant material rich in water content. When the plant material was dried entirely, it has subjected to prepare fine powder with help of mixer grinder. The fine material powder is collected and used for extraction of the crude drug in solvent by soxhlet and maceration extraction method.

DRIED FLOWERS

Soxhlet Extraction:

Soxhlet extraction is a method used to remove active compounds from plant material using heat and continuous solvent washing.

Maceration:

Maceration is a method of extracting compounds by soaking plant material in a solvent at room temperature for a long time.

Soxhlet Extraction

Apparatus:

- Soxhlet extractor
- Round bottom flask
- Condenser
- Heating mantle / water bath, Thimble (filter paper)
- Solvent (ethanol, acetone, etc.)

Procedure:

- Dry and powder the plant material.
- Place the powdered sample inside a thimble.
- Insert the thimble into the Soxhlet extractor.
- Add solvent into the round bottom flask.
- Attach condenser on top.
- Heat the system.
- Solvent evaporates → condenses → drips into thimble.
- When chamber fills, siphon tube returns extract to flask.
- This cycle repeats for 6–8 hours.
- After extraction, evaporate solvent to obtain crude extract.

Advantages

- Efficient extraction
- Uses less solvent
- Continuous extraction

Disadvantages

- Time consuming
- Not suitable for heat-sensitive compounds

Maceration

Apparatus:

- Conical flask / beaker
- Stopper or aluminum foil
- Stirring rod
- Filter paper
- Funnel

Procedure

- Dry and powder plant material.
- Place powder in a flask.
- Add suitable solvent (enough to cover sample).
- Close the flask.
- Keep for 24–72 hours at room temperature.
- Shake occasionally.
- Filter the solution.
- Evaporate solvent to get extract.

Advantages

- Simple method
- No heating required
- Suitable for heat-sensitive compounds

Disadvantages

- Takes longer time
- Less efficient than Soxhlet

Maceration process

Soxhlet method

CONFIRMATION TESTS FOR CRUDE EXTRACTS

Sr. No	CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS	TEST	INFERENCE
1.	ALKALOIDS	Dragendroff's test	+ve
		Mayer's test	+ve
		Wager's test	+ve
		Hager's test	+ve
2.	FLAVANOIDS	Alkaline reagent test	+ve
		Lead acetate test	+ve
3.	SAPONINS	Foam test	-ve
		Emulsification test	+ve
4.	TANNINS	Ferric chloride test	+ve
		Lead acetate test	+ve
5.	GLYCOSIDES	Keller-killianin test (for cardiac glycosides)	-ve
		Borntagger's test (for anthraquinone glycosides)	+ve
6.	PHENOLS	Ferric chloride test	+ve
		Lead acetate test	+ve

METHOD

• In-vitro Anti microbial activity of plant extract

Plant extracts possess significant antimicrobial activity due to compounds like alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins and essential oil, Phenols offering natural alternative to synthetic drugs by inhibiting various bacteria and fungi, targeting pathogens like (BACILLUS, STAPHYLOCOCCUS).

Preparation of nutrient broth medium:

Sr. No	Composition	Standard Formula (1000ml)	Working Formula (500ml)
1	Beef Extract	3 G	1.5 G
2	Peptone	5 G	2.5 G
3	Sodium Chloride	5 G	2.5 G
4	Agar	15 G	7.5 G
5	Distilled Water	1000ml	500ml

PROCEDURE:

- Weigh above all ingredients and make up 500 ml with distilled water.

STANDARD

SAMPLE

STAPHYLOCOCCUS

- Mix well and constant stirring until the power dissolves completely.
- Autoclave the medium at 121 ° C for 15 minutes under 15psi pressure.
- Cool to about 45°C.
- Pour into sterile petri dishes (20ml per plate).
- Spread the microbial suspension evenly over the surface of the agar plate using a sterile swab to create a lawn of growth.
- Incubate at 37 °C for 48hours.

COMMON METHODS:

1. Disc diffusion method (standard-ciprofloxacin, sample-crude drug).
 2. Agar well diffusion method (make small well in the agar & fill with the (standard & sample).
- Measure inhibition zones around plant extract discs and well.
 - Larger zones indicate greater antimicrobial potency.

BACILLUS

STANDARD

SAMPLE

SERIAL DILUTION:

BLANK:

Add 1.5 g of Beef extract
↓
Add 2.5 g of Peptone
↓
Add 2.5 g of Sodium chloride
↓
Make up for 500ml with distilled water
↓
Autoclave the medium at 121°C for 15 minutes
under psi pressure
↓
Cool to about 45-50 °C
↓
Incubate at 37 °C for 48 hours
↓
Measure absorbance at 254nm

CONTROL:

Add 10ml of nutrient broth
↓
Add 0.5ml of Micro-organism (Bacillus,
Staphylococcus)
↓
Incubate at 37 °C for 48hours
↓
Measure the absorbance at 254nm

STANDARD:

Add 10 ml of nutrient broth solution
↓
Add 0.5 ml of micro-organism (bacillus,
staphylococcus)
↓
Add 0.5ml of 50 mcg Ciprofloxacin solution
↓
Incubate at 37 °C for 48 hours
↓
Measure the absorbance at 254nm

TEST:

TEST FOR

100 mcg/ml, 200 mcg/ml, 300 mcg/ml, 400 mcg/ml, 500 mcg/ml, 600 mcg/ml, 700 mcg/ml, 800 mcg/ml, 900 mcg/ml, 1000 mcg/ml.

Add 10ml of nutrient broth solution

↓
Add 0.5ml of micro-organism (Bacillus & Staphylococcus)

↓
Add 0.5ml of plant extract

↓
Incubate at 37 °C for 48 hours

↓
Measure the absorbance at 254nm

RESULT

Sr. No	Sample	Conc (Mcg)	Absorbance (Staphylo Coccus)	Absorbance (Bacillus)	% Inhibition (Staphylo Coccus)	% Inhibition (Bacillus)
	Control		2.1690	2.1690	0%	0%
	Cipro-Floxacin	50	0.4218	0.3042	80.55%	85.97%
1	Test	100	1.4314	1.3812	34.00%	36.32%
2	Test	200	0.8422	0.8599	61.17%	60.35%
3	Test	300	0.8333	0.8448	61.58%	61.05%
4	Test	400	0.7811	0.8183	63.98%	62.27%
5	Test	500	0.7009	0.5114	67.68%	76.42%
6	Test	600	0.6962	0.4227	67.90%	80.51%
7	Test	700	0.6849	0.3826	68.42%	82.36%
8	Test	800	0.4569	0.3809	78.93%	82.43%
9	Test	900	0.4363	0.3042	79.88%	85.97%
10	Test	1000	0.4212	0.1684	80.55%	92.23%

CALCULATION FORMULA:

% of inhibition =

$$\frac{(\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of test}) \times 100}{(\text{Absorbance of control})}$$

OBSERVATION

- Ciprofloxacin at 50µg/ml showed 80-85% inhibition, validation of an assay.

- The plant extract showed dose-dependent inhibition, reaching 80-92% at 1000µg/ml
- This suggests that the extract contains active phytochemicals capable of inhibiting cell wall synthesis, potentially beneficial for managing micro-organism.

GRAPH

DISCUSSION:

1. Phytochemical Analysis

Preliminary phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of:

- Flavonoids
- Alkaloids
- Tannins
- Phenolic compounds
- Terpenoids
- Saponins

These compounds are known for their antimicrobial activity.

2. Antimicrobial Activity (Disc and Agar Well Diffusion Methods)

The antimicrobial activity was tested against:

- Staphylococcus aureus
- Bacillus subtilis

Both disc diffusion and well diffusion methods showed measurable zones of inhibition. Larger zones were observed at higher concentrations of extract. Well diffusion method showed slightly

higher inhibition compared to disc diffusion method. The extract exhibited stronger activity against Staphylococcus aureus than Bacillus subtilis.

3. Serial Dilution and Percentage Inhibition

Serial dilution method was used to determine Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC). As concentration decreased, percentage inhibition also decreased. Highest concentration showed maximum microbial inhibition. MIC was determined as the lowest concentration showing no visible growth. Percentage inhibition was calculated using:

% of inhibition =

$$\frac{\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of test}}{\text{Absorbance of control}} \times 100$$

Results indicated concentration-dependent antimicrobial activity.

4. Molecular Docking Analysis

Major phytochemicals from *Morinda citrifolia* were docked against microbial target proteins. Strong binding affinity was observed. Hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions stabilized

ligand-protein complexes. Docking scores supported the experimental antimicrobial results. This confirms that phytochemicals may inhibit microbial growth by interacting with essential proteins involved in cell wall synthesis and metabolic pathways.

CONCLUSION:

The present study demonstrates that *Morinda citrifolia* (Flowers) possesses significant antimicrobial activity against bacteria. The disc diffusion and well diffusion methods confirmed concentration-dependent inhibition, while serial dilution determined the MIC and percentage inhibition.

Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of bioactive compounds responsible for antimicrobial effects. Molecular docking analysis further supported these findings by showing strong interaction between plant phytoconstituents and microbial target proteins.

Therefore, *Morinda citrifolia* (Flowers) can be considered a promising natural antimicrobial agent and may be used in the development of alternative therapeutic drugs to combat microbial resistance.

REFERENCES

1. Woods GL., In vitro testing of antimicrobial agents, Infectious Disease Clinics of North America, 1995; 9(3):463–481.
2. Leekha S, Terrell CL, Edson RS, General principles of antimicrobial therapy, Mayo Clinic Proceedings, 2011;86(2):156–167.
3. Suresh V, Senthilkumar SK, Jayaseelan K, Johnson Mary A, Punitha Sri R, In-silico and in-vitro evaluation of antidiabetic potential of *Blepharis maderaspatensis* ethanolic extract, World J Pharm Res, 2025;14(16).
4. Houšť J, Spížek J, Havlíček V., Antifungal drugs. *Metabolites*, 2020;10(3):106.
5. Arakawa, Tsutomu; Yamasaki, Hisashi; Ikeda, Keiko; Ejima, Daisuke; Naito, Takeshi; Koyama, A. Hajime, Antiviral and Virucidal Activities of Natural Products, *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, 2009,16 (20): 2485–2497.
6. Kappagoda S, Singh U, Blackburn BG, Antiparasitic therapy, *Mayo Clinic Proceedings*, 2011;86(6):561–583.
7. Kusrini E, Hashim F, Azmi WN, Amin NM, Estuningtyas A. A novel antiamoebic agent against *Acanthamoeba* sp. – a causative agent for eye keratitis infection. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*. 2016;153:714–721.
8. Molina JM, Tourneur M, Sarfati C, et al. Fumagillin treatment of intestinal microsporidiosis. *The New England Journal of Medicine*. 2002;346(25):1963–1969.
9. Antiparasitics. Purdue University Cytology Laboratories. Purdue Research Foundation, 2015.
10. Zich FA, Hyland BPM, Whiffen T, Kerrigan RA. *Morinda citrifolia*. In: *Australian Tropical Rainforest Plants*. 8th ed. Centre for Australian National Biodiversity Research; 2020.
11. *Morinda citrifolia* L. *Flora of China* (eFloras). St. Louis (MO) & Cambridge (MA): Missouri Botanical Garden; Harvard University Herbaria, 2024.
12. Kokat CK. *Pharmacognosy* 16th Edn, NaliPrakasham, Mumbai India 2001.
13. Senthilmurugan GB, Vasanthe B, Suresh K. Screening and antibacterial activity analysis of some important medicinal plants, *International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies* 2013;2(2):146-152.

14. Harborne JB. Phytochemical Method: Modern method Guidelines of plants analysis (Bandung: ITB) Indonesia, 1987.
15. Wang MY, West BJ, Jensen CJ, Nowicki D, Chen SU, Palu AK Anderson G. *Morinda citrifolia* (Noni), A literature review and recent advances in Noni research. *ActaPharmacol Sin.* 23(12); 2002: 1127-114.
16. *Morinda citrifolia* – Indian mulberry. Cook Islands Biodiversity. The Cook Islands Natural Heritage Trust, 2024.
17. Wong KM, et al. Rubiaceae. In: Flora of Singapore. Singapore: Singapore Botanic Gardens; p. 182, 2024.
18. T.P.T. Cushnie et al. Recent advances in understanding the antibacterial properties of flavonoids *International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents*, 2004.
19. T.P.T. Cushnie et al. Antimicrobial activity of flavonoids, *International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents*, 2005.
20. Nita T, Arai T, Takamatsu H, et al. Antibacterial activity of extracts prepared from tropical and subtropical plants on methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Journal of Health Science.* 2002;48:273–276.
21. Atefl DA, Erdoğan ÖT. Antimicrobial activities of various medicinal and commercial plant extracts. *Turkish Journal of Biology.* 2003;27:157–162.
22. Abdulrahman et al., 2010 M.S. Abdulrahman, S. Thangaraj, S.M. Salique, K.F. Khan, S.E. Natheer, Antimicrobial and biochemical analysis of some spices extracts against food spoilage pathogens *Int. J. Food Safety*, 2010, pp. 71-75.
23. Akinpelu et al., 2015 D.A. Akinpelu, O.A. Aiyegoro, O.F. Akinpelu, A.I. Okah, Stem bark extract and fraction of *Persea americana* (Mill) exhibits bactericidal activities against strains of *Bacillus cereus* associated with food poisoning *Molecules*, 2015, pp. 416-429.
24. Marasini B. P., Baral P., Aryal P. et al., Evaluation of antibacterial activity of some traditionally used medicinal plants against human pathogenic bacteria, *BioMed Research International.* 2015, 6, 265425.
25. Romero C. D., Chopin S. F., Buck G., Martinez E., Garcia M., and Bixby L., Antibacterial properties of common herbal remedies of the southwest, *Journal of Ethnopharmacology.* 2005, 99, no. 2, 253–257.
26. Awadh Ali NA, Julich WD, Kusnick C, Lindequist U. Screening of Yemeni medicinal plants for antibacterial and cytotoxic activities. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology.* 2001;74:173–179.
27. Garcia VMN, Gonzalez A, Fuentes M, Aviles R, Rios MY, Zepeda G, Rojas MG. Antifungal activities of nine traditional Mexican medicinal plants. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology.* 2003;87:85–88.
28. Dülger B, Yılmaz F, Gücin B. Antimicrobial activity of the macrofungi *Macrolepiota procera* (Scop. ex Fr.) Sing. *Kükem Dergisi.* 1998;21(1):7–12.
29. S.S. Chang et al, Natural antioxidants from rosemary and sage, *Journal of Food Science*, 1977.
30. H. Kikuzaki et al, Antioxidant Effects of Some Ginger Constituents, *Journal of Food Science*, 1993.
31. Lourdu Jafrin A, Shanti M, Meher Ali R. Anxiolytic effect of ondansetron, a 5-HT₃ antagonist on male albino mice in the elevated plus maze. *Res J Pharm Biol Chem Sci.* 2013;4:1665–75.
32. Vaseghi G, Andalib S, Rabbani M, Sajjadi SE, Jafarian A. Hypnotic Effect of *Salvia reuterana* Boiss for Treatment of Insomnia. *J Med Plants.* 2013; 12:7–13.
33. DeFronzo RA, Ferrannini E, Groop L, Henry RR, Herman WH, Holst JJ, Hu FB, Kahn CR,

- Raz I, Shulman GI, Simonson DC, Testa MA, Weiss R. Type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Nature Reviews Disease Primers*. 2015; 1:15019.
34. Cilla A, Alegría A, De Ancos B, Sánchez-Moreno C, Cano MP, Plaza L, Clemente G, Lagarda MJ, Barbera R. Bioaccessibility of tocopherols, carotenoids, and ascorbic acid from milk- and soy-based fruit beverages: influence of food matrix and processing. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2012;60(29):7282–7290.
35. Hirazumi AY. Antitumor studies of a traditional Hawaiian medical plant, *Morinda citrifolia* (Noni), in vitro and in vivo [dissertation]. Honolulu (HI): University of Hawaii; 1997.
36. Hirazumi, A., E. Furusawa, S.C. Chow & Y. Hokama. 1994. Anticancer activity of *Morinda citrifolia* (noni) in intraperitoneally implanted Lewis lung carcinoma in syngeneic mice. *Proc. West. Pharmacol. Soc.* 37: 145–146.
37. Farine JP, Legal L, Moreteau B, Le Quere JL. Volatile components of ripe fruits of *Morinda citrifolia* and their effects on *Drosophila*. *Phytochem.* 41; 1996: 433.
38. E. Lopez-Oviedo, A.I. Aller, C. Martín, et al. Evaluation of disk diffusion method for determining posaconazole susceptibility of filamentous fungi: comparison with CLSI broth microdilution method *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 50 (2006), pp. 1108-1111.
39. S. Magaldi, S. Mata-Essayag, C. Hartung de Capriles, et al. Well diffusion for antifungal susceptibility testing *Int. J. Infect. Dis.*, 8 (2004), pp. 39-45.
40. Mounyr Balouiri, Moulay Sadiki, Saad Koraichi Ibsouda, Methods for in vitro evaluating antimicrobial activity: A review, *Journal of Pharmaceutical Analysis*, Volume 6, Issue 2, April 2016, Pages 71-79.

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